

A re-examination of Einstein's first derivation of mass–energy equivalence

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Abstract

In 1905, Einstein carried out his first derivation of the mass–energy equivalence by studying in different reference frames the energy balance of a body emitting electromagnetic radiation and assuming special relativity as a prerequisite. In this paper, we prove that a general mass–energy relationship can be derived solely from very basic assumptions, which are the same explicitly or implicitly made in Einstein's derivation but completely neglecting special relativity. The general mass–energy relationship reduces to mass–energy equivalence when it is applied to the case of a body emitting energy in the form of electromagnetic waves. Our main result is that if the core logic behind Einstein's approach is sound, then the essence of the mass–energy equivalence can be derived without special relativity. We then discuss the validity of the assumptions behind the general mass–energy relationship and behind Einstein's derivation and their applicability to energy emission in the form of electromagnetic waves.

Keywords: special relativity · mass–energy equivalence · non-relativistic classical electromagnetism · history of physics · transformation of energy

1 Introduction

Mass–energy equivalence, known in the form of the celebrated equation $E = mc^2$, was derived by Einstein for the first time in a three-page paper published at the end of 1905 [2]. The correctness of this derivation was first criticized by Planck in 1907 [3]. He contended that it is valid “under the assumption permissible only as a first approximation that the total energy of a body is composed additively of its kinetic energy and its energy referred to a system in which it is at rest” [5]. Further criticism was later advanced by Ives in 1952 [4] and Jammer in 1961 [5]: they asserted that Einstein’s derivation was but the result of a *petitio principii*. Several other authors (e.g. G. Holton, H. Arzeliés and A.I. Miller, to name a few) agreed with Ives and Jammer criticism. Recently, however, Stachel and Torretti [6] analyzed Ives’s analysis and concluded that the logic behind Einstein’s derivation is sound. In more recent times, Ohanian [7, 8] agreed with Stachel and Torretti’s criticism of Ives, though he argued that Einstein’s derivation was wrong mainly “because he assumed that the rest-mass change he found when using a non-relativistic, Newtonian approximation for the internal motions of an extended system would be equally valid for relativistic motions”. For a recent review on all Einstein’s conceptual demonstrations of $E = mc^2$, see Hecht [9].

In his first derivation, Einstein considered a body, at rest in an inertial frame S , that emits electromagnetic radiation of total energy L in two equal but oppositely directed amounts. He then considered the same emission process as seen from another inertial frame S' , that of an observer moving with velocity v with respect to the previous stationary inertial frame. In what follows, we briefly review the steps of Einstein’s derivation.

Let there be a stationary body in the system S , and let its energy referred to the system S be E_0 . Let the energy of the body relative to the system S' moving as above with velocity v , be H_0 .

Let this body send out, in a direction making an angle θ with the x -axis, plane waves of light, of energy $\frac{1}{2}L$ measured relatively to S , and simultaneously an equal quantity of plane waves in the opposite direction, for a total emitted energy equal to L (see Fig. 1). Meanwhile, the body remains at rest in S .

Einstein showed that if the radiation is measured in S' , then it possesses a total energy L' that is, neglecting magnitudes of fourth and higher orders in v , equal to

Figure 1: Sketch of the light emission process described in Einstein's paper [2].

$$L' = L \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} \right), \quad (1)$$

where c is the velocity of light. This relation is the approximation to second order in v of the exact result established by using the law for the transformation of the energy of a plane light wave from one inertial frame to the other, derived in the first paper on the special relativity [1].

If we call the energy of the body after the emission of the plane light waves E_1 or H_1 respectively, measured relatively to the system S or S' respectively, then by making use of eq. (1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &= E_1 + L, \\ H_0 &= H_1 + L \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{2c^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

By subtraction, Einstein obtained from these equations the following relation

$$H_0 - E_0 - (H_1 - E_1) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{L}{c^2} v^2. \quad (3)$$

According to Einstein's reasoning, the two differences of the form $H-E$ in eq. (3) have the following simple physical meaning. H and E are the energy values of the same body referred to two reference frames which are in motion relatively to each other, the body being at rest in S . Thus, the difference $H-E$ can differ from the kinetic energy K of the body, with respect to the

system S' , only by an additive constant C , which depends on the choice of the arbitrary additive constants of the energies H and E and does not change during the emission of light. Without loss of generality, this constant can be taken equal to zero. From eq. (3) we have,

$$K_0 - K_1 = \frac{1}{2} \frac{L}{c^2} v^2. \quad (4)$$

What equation (4) tells us is that the kinetic energy of the body with respect to S' diminishes as a result of the emission of the plane light waves, and the amount of diminution is independent of the properties of the body. Moreover, like the kinetic energy, it depends on the relative velocity v . From eq. (4), Einstein's mass-energy equivalence directly follows: if a body gives off the energy L (in the form of radiation), its mass diminishes by $\frac{L}{c^2}$.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we prove that it is possible to derive a general mass-energy relationship by following the logic behind Einstein's original derivation and by applying the same fundamental assumptions (explicit or implicit in Einstein's derivation) but neglecting special relativity. Within the sphere of validity of these basic assumptions, the general mass-energy relationship would still be true even if special relativity would turn out to be false. We also notice that the general mass-energy relationship reduce to mass-energy equivalence when it is applied to the case of a body emitting energy in the form of electromagnetic waves: this is the crucial step in Einstein's first derivation and special relativity plays no fundamental role in the validity of the equivalence.

In Section 3, we show that in the logic of Einstein's first derivation there is at least one assumption that has been unwarrantedly taken as valid also for electromagnetic waves and this is the core of the mass-energy equivalence result. A discussion on the applicability of that (and also another) basic assumption to the emission of electromagnetic waves is given.

In the concluding Section, we summarize our findings.

2 The general mass-energy relationship

It is possible to heuristically derive a general mass-energy relationship by applying the core logic behind Einstein's original derivation but without special relativity. We only use few and very basic initial assumptions which are the

same explicitly or implicitly made in Einstein's derivation, exception made for the peculiar principles of special relativity.

Consider a body stationary in an inertial frame S that emits a total amount of energy equal to L . The energy can be emitted in any imaginable form, but always in equal amounts in opposite directions to maintain a symmetry of emission that intuitively ensures the motionlessness of the body during the process. The equation of the energy balance in S is then $E_0 = E_1 + L$, where E_0 and E_1 are the total energy of the body respectively before and after the emission referred to the system S .

If the same emission process is seen from an inertial reference frame S' in motion with velocity v with respect to S , it is reasonable to expect that the observed *total* emitted energy L' is different from L and greater than that. This is what we heuristically expect in real life simply because the observer is moving with respect to the emitter and some energy is added to what he sees because of that motion. The equation of the energy balance in S' is then $H_0 = H_1 + L'$, where H_0 and H_1 are the total energy of the body respectively before and after the emission referred to the system S' . So far, we have used only the principle of energy conservation in any inertial frame.

Without loss of generality, we can write the mathematical relation that connects L' and L as follows

$$L' = \mathcal{F}(L, v), \tag{5}$$

where \mathcal{F} is a suitable mathematical function.

Let L' be directly proportional to L (**Assumption 1**). If the body emits energy equal to $2L$, the energy observed in S' must be equal to $2L'$. Indeed, this seems a reasonable assumption: the body emitting energy $2L$ can, in theory, be composed of two distinct bodies emitting energy L each. Since in this second case the observer in S' sees an overall energy of $2L'$ (L' for each body), this must be also the case when we have a single body emitting energy equal to $2L$. Thus, equation (5) becomes

$$L' = Lf(v). \tag{6}$$

In order to determine the approximate mathematical form of the dimensionless function $f(v)$, consider the Maclaurin approximation of $f(v)$ within $O(v^3)$

$$f(v) = \alpha + \beta v + \delta v^2 + O(v^3), \tag{7}$$

where α , β and δ are numerical coefficients.

Since $f(0) = 1$, α must be equal to 1. Furthermore, we must have that $f(-v) = f(v)$, since the *overall* energy L' observed by an observer in S' cannot depend upon the arbitrary direction of the velocity of reference frame S' , and thus $\beta = 0$ (also all terms with odd powers must be absent). Therefore,

$$f(v) = 1 + \delta v^2 + O(v^4), \quad (8)$$

with constant δ having the physical units of an inverse square velocity. This velocity is the ‘characteristic velocity’ of the peculiar emission process.

Neglecting magnitudes of fourth and higher orders, we arrive at

$$L' = L(1 + \delta v^2). \quad (9)$$

The derivation of eq. (9) is very general and can be applied to all kind of energy emission mechanisms. As a matter of fact, the way in which it has been obtained is completely independent of the specific energy emission process at play, exception made for the numerical value of the constant δ .

Now, the energy balance equations become

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &= E_1 + L, \\ H_0 &= H_1 + L(1 + \delta v^2). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Like Einstein in his 1905 paper, we subtract the first equation from the second

$$H_0 - E_0 - (H_1 - E_1) = L\delta v^2, \quad (11)$$

and with the assumption that $H - E = K$ (**Assumption 2**) we finally obtain

$$K_0 - K_1 = \frac{1}{2}(2\delta L)v^2. \quad (12)$$

Since the velocity of the body in S' does not change after the emission (it is always v), it must necessarily be also

$$K_0 - K_1 = \frac{1}{2}(-\Delta m)v^2, \quad (13)$$

(it is $-\Delta m$ since $\Delta m = m_1 - m_0$) and thus we arrive at the following mass–energy relationship

$$-\Delta m = 2\delta L. \quad (14)$$

If a body gives off the energy L , its mass diminishes by $2\delta L$. Notice that eq. (14) is not a mass–energy equivalence per se. If we apply eq. (14) to a body releasing two projectiles of mass m in opposite directions with non-relativistic velocity v_0 (relative to the parent body), then it is possible to prove that $\delta = 1/v_0^2$. Since $L = 2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}mv_0^2$ (the emitted energy here is only kinetic), then $-\Delta m = 2m$. Namely, eq. (14) gives simply the change of mass of the parent body due to the loss of two projectiles of mass m each. Thus, in this case eq. (14) does not give any mass–energy equivalence.

On the other hand, if we apply eq. (14) to the emission of energy in the form of electromagnetic waves we obtain a mass–energy equivalence: radiation energy comes from mass reduction and thus mass transforms into radiation energy. Special relativity is not essential for the derivation of this mass–energy equivalence: special relativity comes into play only in the numerical value of the constant δ . The constant δ has the physical units of an inverse square velocity and, in the case of electromagnetic phenomena, it must be heuristically proportional to $1/c^2$. In the case of Einstein’s original derivation, we have that $\delta = 1/2c^2$.

In order to emphasize the implications of the derived general mass–energy relationship, consider that even within Maxwell’s theory of light (and thus, no special relativity) one could have already come to a mass–energy equivalence, albeit in the different form $E = \frac{1}{2}mc^2$.

In fact, within Maxwell’s theory of light (pre-Lorentz, classical ether theory) we have that $\delta = 1/c^2$. The total energy density associated with an electromagnetic wave is

$$u = \frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{1}{2}\frac{B^2}{\mu_0} = \epsilon_0 E^2, \quad (15)$$

since in an electromagnetic wave $E = cB$ and $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}}$ and thus $E = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}}B$, where ϵ_0 and μ_0 are respectively the permittivity and the permeability of free space. Now, consider two plane waves of light, A and B, emitted from the origin of the rest frame S along the x -axis as shown in Fig. 2. Since we are working within Maxwell’s theory of light, frame S shall also be considered as the reference frame of the ether. Consider further a reference frame S' moving away from the origin of S with velocity v in the direction of the positive x -axis. According to the transformation of fields in non-relativistic classical electromagnetism, the components $E'_{A\parallel}$ and $E'_{A\perp}$ of the electric field of wave A in the reference frame S' (see Fig. 2) are

Figure 2: Emission of light waves A and B.

$$\begin{aligned} E'_{A\parallel} &= E_{A\parallel} = 0, \\ E'_{A\perp} &= E_{A\perp} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}_A = E\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

with the substitution $B = E/c$.

The energy density u'_A of wave A measured from S' is then

$$u'_A = \epsilon_0 E^2 \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)^2 = u \left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)^2. \quad (17)$$

By applying the same procedure to wave B, the energy density u'_B is

$$u'_B = \epsilon_0 E^2 \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)^2 = u \left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)^2. \quad (18)$$

In order to calculate the energy of the two plane waves of light, we now need to multiply the energy densities by the volumes of the plane waves measured in S' . After an interval of time T , the wave A has traveled a distance cT from the origin of reference frame S and its volume V is simply $V = AcT$, where A is the transverse area of the wave. For an observer in S' , the volume is the same since, in Maxwell's theory of light, light propagates at speed equal to c only in the ether reference frame S and no Lorentz contraction comes into play.

If the total energy of the two plane waves of light in S is $L = 2uV$, then the total energy measured in S' is

$$\begin{aligned} L' &= u'_A V'_A + u'_B V'_B = u\left(1 - \frac{v}{c}\right)^2 V + u\left(1 + \frac{v}{c}\right)^2 V = \\ &= 2uV\left(1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right) = L\left(1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and thus $\delta = 1/c^2$.

3 Discussion on Assumptions 1 and 2

We now dwell on the applicability of the two assumptions that lurk in the core logic of the previous derivations (Einstein's and that in the present paper), Assumptions 1 and 2.

Let us consider Assumption 2 first, namely Einstein's assumption that $H - E = K$. Without loss of generality, the additive constant C discussed in Section 1 can be taken equal to zero. At first sight, $H - E = K$ appears obvious and necessary. Upon deeper scrutiny, however, it is not. For the sake of derivation, let us rewrite it in the following way

$$H = E + K. \tag{20}$$

In the logic of the derivation, H and E are intended as the total energies of the emitter with respect to reference frames S' and S respectively, from which the energies of the electromagnetic emission L' and L are drawn. With such premises, if we assume the validity of the strict equality in eq. (20), we are implicitly assuming that solely the motion of the body, in the form of its kinetic energy K with respect to S' , does contribute to the increase of the 'internal reservoir' of energy from which the electromagnetic emission originates in S' . This is not problematic in the classical case of emission of energy in mechanical form (e.g. emission of non-relativistic mass projectiles), where both L' and L are kinetic energies. In such cases, the increase of kinetic energy from L to L' directly derives from the increase of kinetic energy of the whole system from E to H .

On the other hand, with electromagnetic emission the consequences implied by assumption (20) are not so obvious and unproblematic. In this case, it is much like to take for granted that the kinetic energy of an electric battery in motion with respect to us can contribute for us to the increase of

the electrical energy content of the battery, or that the kinetic energy of a car in motion with respect to us can contribute for us to the increase of the energy content of the gasoline in the car's gas tank. In [6], the authors try to formally derive Assumption 2 and their approach has been presented as general. However, their treatment does not explicitly address and answer the above question more related to the physics behind the energy balance.

We are not claiming that the kinetic energy of the body does not contribute to the total energy of the body with respect to S' . We are maintaining that if H is intended as the total energy of the system from which the radiation energy L' is drawn in S' , then H cannot be straightly equal to $E + K$. Suppose E to be the internal, metabolic energy of an arm wrestler seated before his contender and K his kinetic energy with respect to a moving observer (the arm wrestler is at rest and the observer is moving). In the observer rest frame, the arm wrestler is not stronger simply because his total energy is now $E + K$. The fact that both E and K have the same physical units (joule) does not automatically imply that one kind of energy can flow into the other.

The validity of strict equality in eq. (20) for electromagnetic radiation is a hidden and not explicitly justified assumption in Einstein's original derivation. The validity of this assumption is crucial for Einstein's derivation of the equivalence between mass and energy. As a matter of fact, according to eq. (9) it always holds that $L' > L$ and

$$|\Delta H| = L' > L = |\Delta E|, \quad (21)$$

and thus $|\Delta H| > |\Delta E|$. This means that, according to eq. (20), the variation of kinetic energy must necessarily be different from zero during the emission process, $\Delta K \neq 0$, and since the velocity of the emitter does not change after the emission, ΔK implies a variation of the mass of the emitter, $\Delta m \neq 0$. Therefore, the assumption that eq. (20) holds for the electromagnetic emission process necessarily leads to Einstein's mass-energy equivalence. In this very peculiar sense, Einstein's original derivation is the result of a *petitio principii*. Our observation here is somewhat reminiscent of Planck's criticism cited in the introduction [3].

Now, since the energy of the electromagnetic emission in S' is greater than that in S and since, as we have suggested above, the assumption of this greater radiation energy coming solely from the kinetic energy of the emitter with respect to S' is unwarranted, where does the energy increase $\Delta L = L' - L$ come from?

In the specific case of electromagnetic radiation, rather than being a feature exclusively related to the intrinsic properties of the emitter, the increase may be a feature proper of the act of observation from a reference frame in motion relative to the emitter along with the application of Maxwell's equations. By the way, equation (20) seems to lose its meaning in the case of a stand-alone electromagnetic wave. If an observer, initially at rest in S , starts moving and becomes an observer stationary in S' , he sees the energy of the stand-alone wave increase from L to L' , but there is no emitter with any increased total internal energy that generates the electromagnetic wave during the act of observation and ΔL is not ascribable to any increase of internal energy of any emitter. The general relation (9) between L' and L (of which eq. (1) is a special case) is obtained without any reference to the properties of the emitting body. It heuristically derives from the intuitive fact that if we observe from a moving reference frame something that has been emitted, we see it as having a different energy for the mere fact that we move with respect to it and not because it has been emitted with higher energy in the first place. This suggests that, in the case of emission of electromagnetic radiation, the increase ΔL in the observed energy is an effect related more to the state of observation and the observer rather than to a change of the internal properties of the emitter.

In order to make this point more circumstantial, take the case of a permanent magnet at rest in an inertial reference frame S [10]. In S , it does not emit any electromagnetic radiation. For an observer moving at constant velocity v with respect to S , however, the permanent magnet does emit electromagnetic radiation. The magnetic field \mathbf{B} generated by the permanent magnet is not uniform in space and thus in the reference frame of the moving observer, we not only have that $\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \neq 0$, but even $\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{B}}{\partial t^2} \neq 0$. The $\frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{B}}{\partial t^2}$ seen by the moving observer is not the result of an explicit time dependence of \mathbf{B} but induced by moving through regions of different spatial field configurations. This, however, does not make any physical difference according to the principle of relativity: the moving observer detects a time-varying \mathbf{B} in his own reference frame and this is all that counts. This means that, according to Maxwell's equations, the moving observer sees induced electromagnetic waves where the stationary observer sees none¹.

¹This may sound bizarre, but it is not. If both the stationary and the moving observer handle a tiny coil, then the moving observer will detect a tiny time-varying *e.m.f.* but the stationary observer will not. We may consider these coils as antennas.

Imagine that the moving observer comes from $+\infty$, passes close to the magnet and eventually moves to $-\infty$. When the observer is still very far from the magnet, he does not detect any noticeable electromagnetic emission and at $+\infty$ the total energy of the magnet from his perspective is H_0 . When the observer is far away at $-\infty$ the total energy of the magnet becomes H_1 with $H_0 = H_1 + L'$, and L' is the overall energy of the electromagnetic radiation detected by the observer during the close encounter with the magnet². In the reference frame of the magnet, however, the total energy related to these two phases are E_0 and E_1 with $E_0 = E_1$. By applying the relation (20) and after the same subtraction made in eqs. (3) and (11), we arrive at $K_0 - K_1 = L'$ and then at $-\Delta m = 2\frac{L'}{v^2}$ (since the velocity of the magnet relative to the moving observer does not change). Thus, according to the observer, the energy of the detected radiation comes from a reduction of the mass of the magnet. On the other hand, in its reference frame the magnet does not do anything and its mass remains constant, $\Delta m = 0$. If it were $\Delta m \neq 0$, the numerical value of Δm would be observer-dependent (since L' is observer-dependent) and this cannot be physically possible. This can be seen as a counterexample of the fact that the increase in the observed energy is exclusively related to the kinetic energy of the emitter and, via $H = E + K$, to its mass.

Suppose that even in the case of permanent magnet we would have

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 &= E_0 + K_0, \\ H_1 &= E_1 + K_1. \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

As we have seen, $E_0 = E_1$ and also $K_0 = K_1$ since $\Delta v = 0$ and $\Delta m = 0$. This means that if the system of equations (22) holds, then we have the paradoxical situation that $H_0 - H_1 = 0$ but also that $H_0 - H_1 = L' \neq 0$. Thus, it must necessarily be $H_0 \neq E_0 + K_0$, namely the total energy H from which the energy of the radiation is drawn in S' cannot be straightly taken equal to the sum $E + K$.

All this also means that even the transformation relations (1) and, in general, (9) may be valid only under certain assumptions that need to be clarified. In what follows, we briefly discuss the general validity of Assumption 1 and venture into a more general derivation of eq. (9) that could also

²By applying the same heuristic reasoning presented in Section 2, it is possible to show that, neglecting magnitudes of fourth and higher orders in the relative velocity v , in this case the energy L' detected by the moving observer depends upon v as $L' = kv^2$, where k is a suitable constant depending also upon the magnetic properties of the specific permanent magnet and the geometry of the close approach.

include cases like that of the permanent magnet.

It has been previously shown that in the case of the permanent magnet the energy L' measured in S' is not directly proportional to the energy L measured in S since $L = 0$ but $L' \neq 0$. Then, let us try to derive a possible more general form of eq. (9). Suppose that

$$L' = \mathcal{F}(L, \mathbf{p}, v), \quad (23)$$

where L is the emitted energy measured in S , v is the velocity of the reference frame S' relative to S and the vector \mathbf{p} represents other physical magnitudes, that may be related to the emitter, on which L' may also depend. The McLaurin series of eq. (23) up to magnitudes of second order in v is

$$L' = A(L, \mathbf{p}) + B(L, \mathbf{p})v + C(L, \mathbf{p})v^2, \quad (24)$$

where A , B and C are suitable functions of L and \mathbf{p} . As has been done in Section 2, the term $B(L, \mathbf{p})$ must be equal to 0, since $L'(v) = L'(-v)$, and the term $A(L, \mathbf{p})$ must be identically equal to L since if $v = 0$, then $L' = L$. Thus,

$$L' = L + C(L, \mathbf{p})v^2. \quad (25)$$

It must be noted that, depending on the values of the parameter \mathbf{p} , $C(0, \mathbf{p})$ can be different from 0, as happens in the case of the permanent magnet where $L = 0$ but $L' \neq 0$. In this case, \mathbf{p} can be related to the magnetic properties of the specific permanent magnet and to the geometry of the close approach of the observer in S' in its motion relative to the magnet.

4 Conclusion

We have shown that a general mass–energy relationship can be heuristically derived by applying the core logic of Einstein’s original derivation with very basic assumptions (explicit or implicit in Einstein’s derivation) but neglecting special relativity. Einstein’s 1905 mass–energy equivalence is a special case of this general relationship: it is the case in which the energy of the body is emitted through electromagnetic radiation. Then, special attention has been paid to one of the basic assumptions behind the derivation: the assumption that the total energy H of the body with respect to a moving observer, and from which the energy of the radiation is drawn, is strictly equal to the energy

E of the body in its rest frame plus the kinetic energy K of the body with respect to the observer. While this is straightforward in cases in which all the energies at play, including the emitted energy, are of mechanical type (non-relativistic kinetic energies), with the emission of energy in the form of electromagnetic waves it is an unwarranted premise, and this premise is crucial in the derivation of Einstein's celebrated result. Through a thought experiment with a permanent magnet, we provide a counterexample of the strict equality $H = E + K$ in the case of energy emitted in the form of electromagnetic waves. All this does not mean that the relation $E = mc^2$ is not physically true in general. We have only shown that the acceptance of Einstein's 1905 derivation may need the acceptance of an unspoken premise whose validity has not been explicitly demonstrated in the original derivation.

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